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An Assessment to Students' Reading Comprehension Strategies Basis for the Development of Remediation Program

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Reading comprehension is a critical skill that support academic success and lifelong learning. Senior high school students now have trouble in interpreting texts. Tavera et al. (2020) stated that developing students' reading comprehension strategies is one of the main goals of education. It appears that the curriculum's main goal is to emphasize students' ability to generate knowledge, analyze critically, and process information. The Department of Education used the Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI), a standard tool, to evaluate students' reading proficiency in a classroom setting. This refers to the revised assessment tool composed of a set of graded passages administered to the whole class and to individual students, which was designed to determine a students' reading comprehension level. In any school, the information gathered from Phil-IRI was an aid for school administration and policy makers in education for appropriate reading activities and to improve student learning success. Based on the results of the Phil-IRI, the discovered challenges in any school are the poor reading comprehension of the students (Luciano, 2019). Hence, teachers were trying to understand the knowledge acquisition and looking for the best techniques and strategies for the students to learn effectively in reading comprehension. Many strategies and techniques were introduced and practiced in the classroom, but there are few that could give more relaxing and enjoyable for both the teacher and the learners to learn effectively. Moreover, reading comprehension also includes the ability of a person to translate the meaning of the sentences using his own words. This also consist of applying the text read in one's life. On one hand, the purpose of comprehension is to understand the text rather than to attain meaning from individual words or sentences, as the outcome serves as a mental representation of a text's meaning combined with the reader's previous knowledge. In the present times, the issue of comprehension is still rampant. Despite being a recognized problem, comprehension is a recurring phenomenon that seems endless even in this modern age, as it is still a widely discussed topic in any academic setting. Many academicians argue why the Philippines is one of the best English-speaking countries globally, ranks lowest in the survey. Education in reading in the Philippines focuses on the primary word definition; this is important, but it is a problem in the context of reading comprehension. Filipino students should be surrounded by essays and try to relate and reflect on them, enhancing their comprehension. By analyzing the specific reading comprehension strategies used by senior high school students, the study can identify common challenges and obstacles they face. It can also encourage the integration of these intervention materials into the curriculum. The objective of these strategies is to analyze comprehension strategies and increase reading comprehension ability of the students. Students can have a better understanding of work instructions and enhance their reading comprehension abilities. They lead better lives, are more useful at work, and communicate well.

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